

Salmonella D Meningitis in an Infant Complicated by Multiple Brain Abscesses: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Salmonella meningitis is a rare but potentially fatal CNS infection in infants. Compared to common neonatal infectious pathogens such as Group B streptococcus and Escherichia coli, Salmonella poses a greater risk of severe complications, including cerebral abscesses, subdural collections, and long-term neurodevelopmental delays. Treatment can be difficult, even with early diagnosis, with no consensus on the optimal course of action.

Case Presentation:

A previously healthy 3-month-old female presented with two days of fever, poor feeding, and irritability. On admission, she was sick-looking with a tense anterior fontanel. High Protein, low glucose, and pleocytosis were revealed on initial CSF analysis, which suggested bacterial meningitis. She required intensive care, mechanical ventilation, and various anticonvulsants due to refractory seizures, even after receiving empiric ceftriaxone and vancomycin. Culture of blood and CSF led to the detection of Salmonella enterica serogroup D, sensitive to ampicillin and gentamicin; the treatment plan was modified accordingly. Neuroimaging discovered bilateral white matter edema, multiple frontal lobe abscesses, and subdural collections, requiring neurosurgical interventions like burr-hole aspiration and drainage. Patient's condition didn't improve with prolonged antimicrobial medication; subsequent follow-ups revealed persistent seizures, developmental delays, including poor head control, and failure to meet milestones on consequent follow-ups.

Discussion:

Salmonella infections typically cause self-limiting gastroenteritis; this case illustrates the rare manifestations of Salmonella D. Diagnosis remains challenging, as clinical manifestations resemble those of more common bacterial meningitis. The prognosis of patients remains poor, with substantial rates of neurological sequelae and high mortality rates. This case emphasizes the importance of suspecting rare etiologies, early diagnosis, repeated neuroimaging, and long-term follow-up to monitor and control complications such as abscesses, empyema, and epilepsy.

Conclusion:

Salmonella meningitis in infants, although rare, poses a high risk of fatality. Thus should be ruled out in suspected cases. Our case shows its aggressive progression, resistance to standard management, and serious neurological complications. Early detection, targeted antibiotics, and neuroimaging are essential; however, long-term outcomes remain uncertain.

Keywords: *Salmonella meningitis, Non-typhoidal Salmonella, Infant meningitis, Brain abscess, Neurodevelopmental sequelae, Epileptic encephalopathy, Pediatric central nervous system infection*

INTRODUCTION:

Salmonella belongs to the Enterobacteriaceae family. They are motile, gram-negative bacilli that commonly

cause gastroenteritis and enteric fever. Salmonella includes multiple serotypes with distinct pathogenic potential and epidemiological features. *Salmonella*

enterica serovars Typhi and Paratyphi cause enteric fever, whereas the many other serovars of *S. enterica* are collectively called non-typhoidal Salmonella (NTS) and typically cause gastroenteritis (and occasionally invasive disease)

Non-typhoidal Salmonella can manifest with bacteremia or extraintestinal infections (i.e, endovascular infection, endocarditis, CNS infection, musculoskeletal infection, visceral infection). Bacteremia manifests with a range of clinical symptoms from fever to sepsis. Non-typhoidal Salmonella bacteraemia can lead to hematogenous seeding, ultimately crossing the blood-brain barrier, causing meningitis. In rare cases, it is complicated by the formation of brain abscess. (1–3).

Group B streptococcus (GBS) and *E. Coli* are the most frequent etiologies of meningitis in infants < 3 months old. Salmonella meningitis is rare and predominantly affects neonates and children less than 12 months of age (4,5). Salmonella accounts for 0.8-6% of all cases of bacterial meningitis, the majority of which occur in infants (6). We present the case of a 3-month-old baby who presented with two days of fever, poor feeding, and irritability. At the hospital, she was sick-looking with a tense anterior Fontanelle. After further diagnostic workup, her CS and blood culture confirmed the diagnosis of bacterial meningitis secondary to Salmonella D infection. Although Salmonella meningitis is rare in

infants, it carries a substantial risk of mortality despite prompt diagnosis and appropriate antimicrobial therapy. This case illustrated the aggressive clinical course, poor response to standard management, and severe neurological complications. While early recognition, pathogen-directed antibiotics, and timely neuroimaging are crucial, long-term neurologic outcomes remain unpredictable.

Case Presentation:

A previously healthy 3-month-old female infant presented on 16 March 2008 with a 2-day history of fever and one day of poor feeding and continuous crying. There were no episodes of vomiting, diarrhea, cough, or convulsions prior to admission. The infant had recently been travelling and returned to Bangalore on 05 March 2008.

She was born at term via normal vaginal delivery with appropriate birth measurements and had completed routine neonatal immunizations, including BCG, hepatitis B, DPT, polio, and *Haemophilus influenzae* type b. She was exclusively breastfed, and her parents were non-consanguineous.

On arrival, the infant appeared sick, irritable, and crying continuously. Her anterior fontanelle was tense, measuring 2 × 3 cm. A small paraumbilical hernia was noted, and the liver was just palpable. Cardiovascular and respiratory examinations were unremarkable, and oxygen saturation on room air was normal.

Table 1: Baseline Hematological and Biochemical Investigations at Admission

Parameter	Result	Reference Range (Infant)
White blood cell Count	4.6 ×10 ³ /μL	6-17 ×10 ³ /μL
Hemoglobin	9 g/dL	10.5-14 g/dL
Platelet Count	166 ×10 ³ /μL	150-400 ×10 ³ /μL
Sodium (Na ⁺)	133 mmol/L	135-145 mmol/L
Potassium (K ⁺)	4.4 mmol/L	3.5-5.5 mmol/L
Chloride (Cl ⁻)	108 mmol/L	98-107 mmol/L
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ ⁻)	20 mmol/L	22-28 mmol/L
Random blood glucose	143 mg/dL	70-140 mg/dL

Table 2: Cerebrospinal Fluid Findings at Presentation

Parameter	Result	Reference Range
Protein	300 mg/dL	15-45 mg/dL
Glucose	<10 mg/dL	45-80 mg/dL

Concurrent blood glucose	143 mg/dL	70-140 mg/dL
CSF/ blood glucose ratio	0.06	≥0.6
Total WBC	700 /cmm	0-5 /cmm
Differential count	50% polymorphs, 50% lymphocytes	Predominantly lymphocytes
RBC	300 /cmm	0 /cmm
Gram stain	No organism seen	No organism
Bacterial antigen test	Negative	Negative

She was initially managed as septic meningitis and started on ceftriaxone and vancomycin, along with supportive therapy including mannitol, ranitidine, and intravenous fluids.

On the second hospital day (17 March 2008), she developed repeated convulsions, increasing irritability, and a bulging anterior fontanelle, along with hypotension,

which required a transfer to the ICU. She was started on phenobarbitone, phenytoin, dexamethasone, and additional measures were taken to control the intracranial pressure. A computed tomography (Fig.1) was done, which showed bilateral frontal hypodensities consistent with white matter edema, without hemorrhage or collections.

Fig.1 Hypodensity in both frontal regions, suggestive of bilateral white matter edema

During 18–19 March, the frequency of seizures increased, becoming focal, predominantly affecting the right lower limb. The infant required intubation and was placed on a midazolam infusion. Cultures of the blood and CSF later grew *Salmonella* group D, leading to modification of therapy: ampicillin and gentamicin were added, and vancomycin was discontinued. Intravenous immunoglobulins were initiated. Despite sedation, she continued to have brief intermittent seizures, prompting adjustment of antiepileptic medication doses. She also received albumin supplementation for persistent hypoalbuminemia. By 25 March 2008, no further seizures were observed. She remained hemodynamically stable but showed reduced spontaneous movement of the left side. On 27 March, she was afebrile, tolerating full nasogastric feeds, and her anterior fontanelle was no longer bulging.

Between 28 and 30 March, the infant experienced two brief fever spikes. Repeat lumbar puncture showed persistent abnormalities, though no organisms were seen.

Table 3: Cerebrospinal Fluid Findings on Repeat Lumbar Puncture (28/03/2008)

Parameter	Result	Reference Range
Protein	250 mg/dL	15-45 mg/dL
Glucose	16 mg/dL	45-80 mg/dL
Concurrent blood glucose	68 mg/dL	70-140 mg/dL
CSF/ blood glucose ratio	0.23	≥0.6
Total WBC	150 /cmm	0-5 /cmm
Gram stain	No organism seen	No organism

A repeat CT scan on 01 April 2008 (Fig.2) revealed multiple bilateral frontal lobe abscesses and a left-sided subdural collection.

Fig.2 Multiple bilateral frontal lobe abscesses & Left-sided subdural collection

Neurosurgical consultation was obtained. A brief trial of ciprofloxacin was discontinued due to increasing intracranial pressure, and meropenem was initiated. She continued on phenobarbitone and phenytoin. Soon afterward, the family traveled back to their home city, where aspiration of the intracerebral abscesses was performed.

A CT scan on 27 May 2008 (Fig.3) demonstrated near-complete evacuation of the abscesses, residual hypodense areas with small calcifications, an enlarged left subdural collection with septations, and bilateral ventricular enlargement. She subsequently underwent burr-hole aspiration and drainage of the subdural collection at the hospital.

Fig.3 Areas of hypodensities and minute calcifications

A postoperative CT scan performed on 30 May 2008 showed that the infant still had a chronic left parieto-occipital subdural collection, with new areas suggesting acute rebleeding as well as intracavitary air. The scan also demonstrated bifrontal encephalomalacia and periventricular calcifications, but importantly, there was no evidence of midline shift.

By 12 June 2008, her neurological assessment revealed a worrying progression of deficits. She displayed myoclonic jerks, did not maintain eye contact, and had generalized hypertonia with hyperreflexia. Muscle strength was notably reduced—grade II power in the upper limbs and grade III in the lower limbs. An EEG showed hypersarrhythmia, consistent with a severe epileptic encephalopathy. Based on these findings, her treatment was adjusted: vigabatrin (Sabril) and valproate were started, while phenobarbitone and phenytoin were gradually withdrawn.

By July 2008, follow-up imaging demonstrated a decrease in the size of the subdural hematoma, suggesting partial resolution. However, at a developmental review on 26 August 2008, although her seizure frequency had improved, she continued to show significant global developmental delay. She was still unable to sit independently, hold objects, or lift her head while lying prone. In light of this, she was referred for physiotherapy and home-based rehabilitation on 24 September 2008.

Toward the end of 2008, her developmental progress remained severely limited. She had poor head control, could only sit momentarily with support, and was still unable to transfer objects between her hands. Her visual tracking and fixation were also poor. Additionally, her head circumference remained below the 3rd percentile, highlighting the ongoing concerns about impaired brain growth.

Figure 4. Timeline of disease progression and major therapeutic interventions in an infant with Salmonella enterica serogroup D meningitis

DISCUSSION:

Salmonella enterica (serogroup D) meningitis remains clinically significant, as illustrated by our case, the clinical manifestation may resemble or mimic other more common causes of bacterial meningitis (e.g., Streptococcus pneumoniae, Haemophilus influenzae type b, or Neisseria meningitidis). The common non-specific symptoms of these bacterial infections include fever, irritability, and a bulging fontanelle. Common CSF findings include neutrophilic pleocytosis, elevated protein, and low glucose levels. Moreover, the clinical and laboratory characteristics “were similar to other causes of bacterial meningitis” in a review of 13 infants with Salmonella meningitis (ages 3 days - 9 months)(7). Salmonella meningitis is a worrisome diagnosis for pediatricians to make, as they know its potential for severe intracranial complications and poor long-term neurological prognosis. In a retrospective review, Subdural effusion/empyema, ventriculitis, hydrocephalus, intracerebral hemorrhage, and cerebral abscess were reported, along with a high mortality rate of 18%. From the patients who survived, more than half had relatively long-term outcomes, but the rest suffered from adverse long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes (7). Our patient suffered from bilateral white-matter edema, multiple frontal lobe abscesses, subdural collections, and subsequent periventricular calcifications with encephalomalacia, all these findings are consistent with the range of complications described.

A study of 24 infants from Taiwan reported that approximately 25% of infants developed focal intracranial infection (subdural empyema or brain abscess). These infants concurrently suffered from prolonged seizures, and many of them also experienced ventriculitis or cerebral infarction. Long-term follow-up in that cohort revealed significant neurodevelopmental deficits, including developmental delay in 67% of the survivors, 48% suffered from motor impairment, 33% developed epilepsy, and other notable complications were

hearing loss, visual deficits, hydrocephalus, cranial nerve palsy, and microcephaly (8). Similar to the poor outcome pattern in this literature, our patient's course included refractory seizures, need for neurosurgical drainage, persistent subdural collection, encephalomalacic changes, periventricular calcifications, microcephaly (head circumference <3rd centile), global developmental delay, and epileptic encephalopathy. The wide array of symptoms and findings seen in Salmonella meningitis patients makes it quite difficult for clinicians to suspect Salmonella infections; thus, it is important to have a systematic approach and rule out fatal diseases like Salmonella meningitis early to achieve a better prognosis. These findings align with previously reported isolated case reports of Salmonella-associated brain abscess or subdural empyema. For example, a 4-week-old infant was reported to have developed several cerebral abscesses, necessitating an extended period of antibiotic therapy and neurosurgical drainage (9). Another case report described a 6-month-old infant who developed a parietal brain abscess. Despite surgical drainage and long-term antibiotic therapy, the condition persisted (10).

Studies report that invasive non-typhoidal Salmonella (iNTS) causing meningitis may have a higher incidence of focal intracranial complications and long-term morbidity, compared to the usual self-limiting Salmonella gastroenteritis (11,12).

Furthermore, compared to older children, infants (especially <1 year) have a significantly increased risk of neurological sequelae (subdural effusion/empyema, hydrocephalus, seizures, long-term cognitive impairment), according to findings from an investigation of general bacterial meningitis in children (13). Poor outcomes can be predicted by several factors, including delayed presentation, diminished consciousness, seizures, and prolonged duration before starting appropriate medication (8,11,13). Some of these risk factors likely contributed to the unfavorable outcome in our patient, as she had intracranial hypertension, developed focal

intracranial infections requiring surgical drainage, developed recurrent refractory seizures requiring prolonged sedation and intensive care with mechanical ventilation. Although treatment was initiated at the appropriate time, other risk factors outweighed this positive aspect.

Treatment of Salmonella meningitis remains difficult, with no agreement on the most effective regimen or duration. Previous studies found that using ampicillin and/or chloramphenicol for an insufficient duration was linked to relapse (7,14). In cases where the patient's condition is complicated by abscess or empyema, extended antibiotic courses (typically several weeks) have been paired with neurosurgical drainage (9,10,15).

A recent study suggested that antibiotic therapy for Salmonella meningitis might need to be extended to 4-6 weeks, especially if intracranial complications are observed (16,17). Carbapenems (e.g., Meropenem) and fluoroquinolones (e.g., Ciprofloxacin) have been administered successfully in some cases, particularly when third-generation cephalosporins fail to elicit an adequate response or when neurosurgical intervention is required (10,11,15). Therapy was adjusted in our patient's management after a culture of blood and CSF showed ampicillin and gentamicin sensitivity. Later, due to the development of multiple abscesses and subdural collection, therapy was increased with the addition of meropenem and neurosurgical drainage. However, neurological recovery remained poor, emphasizing the limited efficacy of exclusive antibiotic therapy in treating severe focal intracranial complications caused by Salmonella meningitis. Adjunctive therapy, including neurosurgical drainage, sedation, mechanical ventilation, and intensive conservative treatment, is necessary to have a better prognosis in complicated cases.

This case illustrates the significance of repeated neuroimaging during the clinical course of a complicated case of Salmonella meningitis. The initial CT scan revealed only white matter edema. Subsequent imaging over the following days revealed several abscesses and subdural collections, prompting the clinician to recommend surgical intervention. Previous studies have described a similar time-dependent evolution seen in imaging (9,10,14). Clinicians need to maintain a high index of suspicion for Salmonella (including nontyphoidal, serogroup D) as a cause of meningitis in infants, even in the absence of prior episodes of gastroenteritis or diarrhea. This pattern is also noticed in several reported series where infants didn't exhibit any gastrointestinal symptoms (7,18). Early lumbar puncture and culture (blood and/or CSF) is essential in differentiating from more common bacterial pathogens. Empiric treatment covering the most common meningitis

pathogens should be started as soon as bacterial meningitis is suspected, but when Salmonella is identified antibiotic regimen should be modified according to the culture findings.

Moreover, long-term follow-up is essential, considering the high risk of potentially fatal neurodevelopmental sequelae(19), to modify the treatment regimen according to the patient's condition and to also recommend non-medical therapy (speech therapy, physical therapy for gait and balance). Establishing a long-term developmental monitoring and rehabilitative plan is especially crucial in limited-resource settings or where patients may be transferred or lost during follow-up. Our patient was referred for physiotherapy and home-based rehabilitation, but the severity of her deficits emphasizes how limited the potential for full recovery may be.

Psychological and Neurodevelopmental Profile:

The severe neuroinflammatory insult of Salmonella meningitis in infancy initiates a complex, lifelong condition characterized by profound, multi-domain impairments that extend far beyond the acute infectious period (20). The presented case of a 3-month-old infant, who developed bilateral frontal encephalomalacia, infantile spasms, and left-sided hemiparesis, exemplifies this devastating trajectory (6). The resulting neurodevelopmental and psychosocial profile imposes a significant burden on the child's potential and the family system, necessitating a structured, lifelong care paradigm (21).

The injury directly disrupts the acquisition of early motor and cognitive milestones. The infant's global developmental arrest, manifesting as an inability to achieve head control, sitting, or grasping, is a direct consequence of diffuse brain injury (22). Such outcomes are quantifiably common; a pivotal 12-year study of infant Salmonella meningitis survivors found that 48% had motor disabilities and 52% had language disorders at school age (8). This aligns with broader evidence that bacterial meningitis survivors have a mean IQ approximately 5.5 points lower than controls and are nearly five times more likely to have an intellectual disability (IQ < 70) (23). The co-occurrence of infantile spasms, an epileptic encephalopathy with a known symptomatic etiology (prior brain injury), creates a vicious cycle, where ongoing seizures further disrupt neural network organization and compound developmental delay (24).

Cognitive and motor challenges are compounded by sensory impairments. The case notes "poor vision," but the spectrum of deficits is broad (25). Sensorineural hearing loss affects a substantial minority (approximately 17%) of survivors, and imbalances in tactile and proprioceptive processing due to spasticity are common (8). This sensory dysregulation impedes environmental

exploration and hinders communication, exacerbating developmental delays (22). Furthermore, this profile creates severe barriers to secure infant-caregiver bonding. The child's capacity for reciprocal social engagement, through eye contact, social smiling, or calm feeding, is compromised by neurological injury, sensory overload, and medication effects (22). For parents, the journey from a healthy infant to managing a life-altering chronic condition is profoundly traumatic, leading to high rates of chronic stress, anxiety, and caregiver burnout as they navigate complex medical care and grieve lost developmental milestones (26).

Consequently, systematic, multidisciplinary follow-up is not optional but essential (21). Acute inpatient management is merely the first phase. Survivors require proactive, coordinated monitoring by pediatric neurology, developmental medicine, and allied therapies to manage epilepsy, implement early intervention, and address sensory deficits (27). Aggressive management of infantile spasms is paramount to mitigate further encephalopathic disruption (24). Crucially, ongoing neuropsychological assessments are needed to identify evolving "silent" deficits, such as specific learning disabilities or executive dysfunction, which may not be apparent in early childhood but critically impact educational attainment and life chances (23). This holistic, sustained approach is the cornerstone of mitigating disability and supporting the well-being of both the child and their family (26).

CONCLUSION:

Salmonella enterica serogroup D meningitis, despite being rare in infancy, is a highly aggressive infection of the central nervous system with a significant risk of intracranial complications and long-term neurological morbidity. This case demonstrates how fulminant disease can develop even in the presence of prompt diagnosis, appropriate antibiotic treatment, and intensive conservative management. The invasiveness of nontyphoidal *Salmonella* in infants is highlighted by the quick progression from meningitis to refractory seizures, multifocal brain abscesses, subdural collections, and ultimately encephalomalacia.

The clinical course of our patient is consistent with patterns reported in the literature, such as the recurrent requirement for neurosurgical intervention, the need for protracted and escalating antibiotic regimens, and poor response to standard third-generation cephalosporins. Significantly, recurrent neuroimaging was essential in detecting developing focal intracranial complications that were not seen on preliminary scans, highlighting the need for careful radiological monitoring in complicated cases. The limited reversibility of substantial inflammatory brain injury is reflected in the persistence of severe neurodevelopmental sequelae, such as epileptic encephalopathy, microcephaly, and global developmental

delay, even after microbiological clearing and surgical interventions.

This case highlights the need for increased clinical suspicion for *Salmonella* meningitis in infants who present with severe bacterial meningitis, even in the absence of gastrointestinal symptoms. Essential elements of care include early pathogen-directed treatment, long-term antibiotics, prompt neurosurgical consultation, and structured long-term neurodevelopmental follow-up. Finally, better results will rely on integrated multidisciplinary rehabilitation techniques targeted at reducing patients' lifelong disability in addition to acute management.

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